

Effect of insecticides on *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spore germination, IRRI, 1983.

Insecticide	Spore germination ^a (%)			
	Insecticide mixed with media ^b		Insecticide on media surface ^c	
	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>
	<i>Recommended for BPH control^d</i>			
Monocrotophos	0 c	32 b	72 b	95 b
BPMC	1 b	2 c	36 d	36 d
Carbosulfan	0 c	0 d	66 c	68 c
Azinphos ethyl + BPMC	0 c	0 d	28 e	68 c
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	0	9	51	67
	<i>Causing BPH resurgence^e</i>			
Azinphos ethyl	20 d	71 c	16 d	77 c
Deltamethrin	56 c	90 b	81 b	89 b
Methyl parathion	0 e	6 e	15 d	72 d
MIPC	66 b	38 d	75 c	67 e
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	36	51	47	77

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. 300 random spores counted 24 h after insecticide application. ^bInsecticide mixed with the culture media at 40-45°C, then plated. Fungal spore suspension (0.3 ml/petri dish) was spread on the cooled and hardened media. ^cInsecticides and fungi spores were mixed together in suspension and 0.3 ml/petri dish was spread on top of the hardened culture media. ^dAt the national recommended rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha. ^eAt the minimal rate that causes resurgence (0.50 kg ai/ha, except deltamethrin at 0.025 kg ai/ha).

Influence of flooding, fertilizer, and plant spacing on insect pest incidence

P. Karuppuchamy and S. Uthamasamy, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

We studied the influence of cultural methods on reducing insect pest incidence in rice in 1981 kuruvai.

Continuous flooding and alternate flooding and draining; 15- × 10-cm, 20-

× 10-cm, and 30- × 10-cm spacing (water regimes and spacings were main plots); 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha; and 42 and 83 kg K/ha (N and K treatments were sub-plots) were tested in a split-plot design with 3 replications. TKM9 was planted in 1 6-m² plots. Tillers and silvershoots were counted in 19 randomly chosen hills/plot 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). Populations of green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH), and whorl maggot (WM) damaged leaves on 10 hills/

Insect population and grain yield as determined by cultural practice, Aduthurai, India.^a

Treatment	GLH/10 hills	BPH/10 hills	WM (% damaged leaves)	GM (% silvershoots)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Water management</i>					
Continuous flooding	19 b	9 b	7 b	2a	5.6 a
Alternate flooding and draining	13 a	4a	4a	3 b	4.9 b
<i>Spacing</i>					
15 × 10 cm	13 a	6	5	3	5.0
20 × 10 cm	18 b	6	6	2	5.2
30 × 10 cm	18 b	6	5	3	5.5
<i>N level</i>					
50 kg/ha	15 a	3a	5	2	4.8 b
100 kg/ha	16 a	7 b	5	2	5.2 b
150 kg/ha	18 b	8 c	5	3	5.7 a
<i>K level</i>					
42 kg/ha	17	6	5	2	5.2
83 kg/ha	16	6	5	3	5.3

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

cides. Recommended insecticides reduced spore germination more than resurgence-causing insecticides did, probably because a higher dosage of the recommended insecticide was applied.

Because both types of insecticides greatly inhibited spore germination of both fungi, it is unlikely that insecticides cause resurgence by counteracting the beneficial effect of entomogenous fungi. Among the BPH resurgence-causing insecticides, deltamethrin, the most powerful, had the weakest effect on spore germination. Only methyl parathion, the second most powerful BPH resurgence-causing insecticide, greatly reduced spore germination. □

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

plot were counted 20, 45, and 70 DT. Grain yield was recorded.

Alternate flooding and draining significantly reduced GLH and BPH populations and WM damage. The 10- × 15-cm spacing reduced GLH numbers (see table). The BPH population increased with N application. K did not influence insect damage or grain yield. Increased gall midge (GM) incidence in plots with intermittent flooding may have been caused by a change in microclimate, and yield reduction may have been caused by hardening of the soil. □

Effect of organophosphatic insecticides on the yellow stem borer (YSB) eggs and parasites

N. C. Patnaik and J. M. Satpathy, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

Insecticides used in rice fields often kill nontarget insect species. We studied the effect of seven insecticides on YSB eggs and egg parasite *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae). Field

parasitized YSB egg masses were collected in an unsprayed area of the University research farm. In the laboratory, 3 egg masses of uniform size, each attached in situ to a rice leaf, were kept on filter paper in a 7.5 cm-diam petri dish and exposed to the insecticide solution under a Potter's spray tower. After drying, the egg masses were incubated in rearing tubes at 29°C and 55% relative humidity. Each set of three was replicated thrice and an unsprayed set of three egg masses was kept for comparison. Emerged parasites, borer larvae, and unemerged larvae were counted after the unemerged larvae were softened in diluted potassium hydroxide.

Treated egg masses yielded a high percentage of parasites and host larvae in all test concentrations. In general, host larva and parasite emergence was significantly lower in the treated set than in the untreated (see table). The varying rate of parasite emergence in the insecticide treatments and the untreated set was caused by the difference in field parasitization rate rather than by the insecticides. Insecticide action on developing parasites

Percent emergence of larvae and parasite adults from insecticide-treated and untreated host eggs at Bhubaneswar, India, Feb 1982.

Insecticide	Concentration (ai %)	Emergence (%)			
		Larvae		Adults	
		Eggs (treated)	Eggs (untreated)	Eggs (treated)	Eggs (untreated)
Chlorpyrifos	0.025	32.7	50.0	10.3	32.6
	0.050	56.0	57.1	6.0	12.2
	0.075	22.2	85.7	50.0	46.8
Fenitrothion	0.025	24.5	2.4	11.6	20.0
	0.050	43.8	48.5	30.1	81.3
	0.075	33.5	35.7	41.1	60.0
Fenthion	0.025	22.6	59.1	45.4	12.0
	0.050	67.6	76.9	70.9	65.0
	0.075	49.8	59.0	66.7	82.4
Formothion	0.025	43.6	78.6	60.2	63.6
	0.050	24.4	52.8	36.0	20.0
	0.075	22.3	74.1	51.5	54.7
Phenthoate	0.025	77.5	53.6	47.1	66.7
	0.050	28.0	26.8	26.0	30.0
	0.075	33.1	91.0	73.4	66.7
Phosphamidon	0.025	16.4	11.1	17.2	28.6
	0.050	49.5	60.0	63.6	12.0
	0.075	53.6	43.3	43.5	60.0
Quinalphos	0.025	19.2	39.3	25.0	77.5
	0.050	32.7	44.8	41.3	38.5
	0.075	82.1	97.7	47.6	58.5
LSD 5%	Insecticide		2.6		2.3
	Untreated vs treated		0.8		0.7
	Interaction		3.6		3.2

and host eggs was adequately circumvented by the hairy matrix surrounding

the egg mass. The chorion of the egg may also have limited insecticide penetration. □

Insect pests of rice in the Sikkim Hills

N. S. Azad Thakur, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex for NEH Region, Shillong 793013, India

Surveys from 1977 to 1981 in hilly rice growing areas in Sikkim identified many insect species (see table). Few insects had pest status. Stem borers *Chilo suppressalis* (Walk.), *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.), and *Sesamia inferens* (Walk.) were the major pests. They cause 7.2% deadhearts at tillering and 19.5% whiteheads after flowering. Leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guen.) was a serious pest in Jul 1979, with 22.3 larvae/m² in Ranipul. Usually it is of minor importance. Brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horv.) were generally minor pests, but in 1978 WBPH infestation was high. Gall midge, caseworm, grasshopper, rice bugs, rice hispa, rice leafhoppers, semilooper, spittle bug, leaf beetles, and rice skipper were of minor importance. □

Rice insects in the Sikkim hills.

Common name	Scientific name	Family	Order	% infestation
Striped stem borer	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walk.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Tussock caterpillar	<i>Euproctis varians</i> (Walk.)	Lymantiridae	Lepidoptera	—
Pink stem borer	<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walk.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Rice swarming caterpillar	<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisd.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Common cutworm	<i>S. litura</i> (F.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Ear-cutting caterpillar	<i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walk.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Semilooper	<i>Mocis</i> [=Remigia] <i>frugalis</i> (Fabr.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice skipper	<i>Parnara guttata</i> Bremer & Grey	Hesperiidae	Lepidoptera	—
Yellow stem borer	<i>Scirpophaga</i> [=Tryporyza] <i>incertulas</i> (Walk.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Leaf folder	<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice caseworm	<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice bug	<i>Leptocorisa</i> sp.	Alydidae	Hemiptera	12 to 15
Stink bug	<i>Cletus</i> sp.	Coreidae	Hemiptera	—
Spittle bug	<i>Cosmoscarta</i> sp.	Cercopidae	Hemiptera	—
Brown planthopper	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Delphacidae	Hemiptera	—
Whitebacked planthopper	<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horv.)	Delphacidae	Hemiptera	—
Leaf rolling weevils	<i>Centrocorynus scutellaris</i> (Gyll)	Attellabidae	Coleoptera	—
	<i>C. rufulus</i> Voss.	Attellabidae	Coleoptera	—
Root weevil	<i>Phytoscaphus triangularis</i> (Oliv.)	Curculionidae	Coleoptera	—
Rice gall midge	<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Cecidomyiidae	Diptera	—
Green leafhopper	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål)	Cicadellidae	Homoptera	—
Zigzag leafhopper	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i> (Motsch.)	Cicadellidae	Homoptera	—
Aphid	<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i> (Linnaeus)	Aphididae	Homoptera	—
Small grasshopper	<i>Oxya chinensis</i> (Thunberg)	Acrididae	Orthopter	5 to 8